

URBAN CULTURE AND THE MODERN HUMAN PSYCHE IN THE
POETRY OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Aleksandr Faynberg she'riyatida shahar madaniyati va zamonaviy inson ruhiyatining badiiy talqini tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda shoir lirikasida shahar obrazining poetik makon sifatidagi o'rni, urbanistik muhitning inson ichki dunyosiga ta'siri hamda zamonaviy insonning ruhiy kechinmalari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Faynberg ijodida shahar hayoti tasvirlari orqali insoniy qadriyatlar, falsafiy mushohada va gumanistik g'oyalar ifodalanishi ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi. Maqolada shoir she'riyatining badiiy xususiyatlari, obrazlilik va poetik tasvir vositalari tahlil qilinib, uning zamonaviy adabiyotdagi o'rni ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Aleksandr Faynberg, she'riyat, shahar madaniyati, urbanistik motivlar, zamonaviy inson ruhiyati, poetik obraz, falsafiy lirika, badiiy tasvir vositalari, gumanistik g'oyalar.

Annotation. This article analyzes the artistic interpretation of urban culture and modern human psyche in the poetry of Alexander Feinberg. The study highlights the role of the image of the city as a poetic space in the poet's lyrics, the influence of the urban environment on the inner world of man, and the spiritual experiences of modern man. Also, the expression of human values, philosophical observations, and humanistic ideas through images of urban life in Feinberg's work is scientifically substantiated. The article analyzes the artistic features of the poet's poetry, imagery, and poetic means of imagery, and reveals its place in modern literature.

Keywords. Alexander Feinberg, poetry, urban culture, urban motifs, modern human psyche, poetic image, philosophical lyrics, means of artistic imagery, humanistic ideas

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется художественная интерпретация городской культуры и современной человеческой психики в поэзии Александра Файнберга. Исследование освещает роль образа города как поэтического пространства в лирике поэта, влияние городской среды на внутренний мир человека и духовные переживания современного человека. Также научно обосновывается выражение человеческих ценностей, философских наблюдений и гуманитарных идей через образы городской жизни в творчестве Файнберга. В статье анализируются художественные особенности, образность и поэтическая образность поэзии поэта и раскрывается её место в современной литературе.

Ключевые слова: Александр Файнберг, поэзия, городская культура, городские мотивы, современная человеческая психика, поэтический образ, философская лирика, художественная образность, гуманитарные идеи.

Introduction. One of the creators who occupied an important place in the Uzbek and Russian literary relations of the 20th century is Alexander Feinberg. His poetry is distinguished by its artistic expression of the subtle feelings of the human soul, philosophy of life, and spiritual landscapes of the modern urban environment. In the poet's work, the city appears not only as a place, but also as an important poetic image expressing the spiritual state of man. Urbanistic motifs, that is, urban life, its cultural environment, and its impact on the human psyche, are one of the topical issues in modern literature. In this regard, the analysis of Feinberg's poetry is of great importance in understanding the spiritual experiences of modern man.

In Feinberg's poetry, images of the city are often given a vivid, emotional and philosophical interpretation. The poet reveals the inner world of a person by describing city streets, squares, and scenes of ordinary life. For Feinberg, the city is not a simple geographical space, but an environment where different characters, destinies, and spiritual experiences intersect. Through the noise of the street, night lights, and scenes of busy life, the poet expresses the feelings of loneliness, search, and hope of a modern person. In the poet's poems, a modern person is often depicted as a person who observes his life and seeks the meaning of life. Although the urban environment encourages a person to be active, it sometimes also increases his inner loneliness. In Feinberg's lyrics, the human soul is revealed through subtle psychological observations. The poet often expresses deep human spiritual experiences through ordinary events or

landscapes. This aspect gives his poetry a philosophical spirit. Another important feature of Feinberg's poetry is the expression of urban culture through artistic images. The poet uses such artistic means as metaphor, symbol, and contrast to show various aspects of urban life. For example, nighttime cityscapes are often depicted in harmony with a person's inner thoughts. This method allows the reader to feel the connection between the external landscape of urban life and the human soul.

In conclusion, the poetry of Alexander Feinberg is distinguished by its deep artistic interpretation of the modern urban environment. The poet expresses the human psyche, philosophy of life, and the problems of modern society through urban landscapes. In Feinberg's lyrics, the city is not an ordinary place, but a poetic image reflecting human spiritual experiences. In this regard, his poetry is an example of creativity that has made a worthy contribution to the development of urban motifs in modern literature.

Kirish. XX asr o'zbek va rus adabiy aloqalarida muhim o'rin egallagan ijodkorlardan biri — Aleksandr Faynberg hisoblanadi. Uning she'riyati inson qalbining nozik kechinmalari, hayot falsafasi hamda zamonaviy shahar muhitining ruhiy manzaralarini badiiy ifodalashi bilan ajralib turadi. Shoir ijodida shahar nafaqat makon, balki inson ruhiy holatini ifodalovchi muhim poetik obraz sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Zamonaviy adabiyotda urbanistik motivlar, ya'ni shahar hayoti, uning madaniy muhiti va inson ruhiyatiga ta'siri dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Shu jihatdan Faynberg she'riyatini tahlil qilish zamonaviy insonning ruhiy kechinmalarini anglashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Faynberg she'riyatida shahar obrazlari ko'pincha jonli, hissiy va falsafiy talqin bilan beriladi. Shoir shahar ko'chalarini, maydonlarini, oddiy hayot manzaralarini tasvirlash orqali insonning ichki dunyosini ochib beradi. Shahar Faynberg uchun oddiy geografik makon emas, balki turli xarakterlar, taqdirar va ruhiy kechinmalar kesishgan muhitdir. Ko'cha shovqini, tungi chiroqlar, gavjum hayot manzaralari orqali shoir zamonaviy insonning yolg'izlik, izlanish va umid kabi tuyg'ularini ifodalaydi. Shoir she'rlarida zamonaviy inson ko'pincha o'z hayoti haqida mushohada yurituvchi, hayot ma'nosini izlovchi shaxs sifatida tasvirlanadi. Urbanistik muhit insonni faollikka undasa-da, ba'zan uning ichki yolg'izligini ham kuchaytiradi. Faynberg lirikasida inson qalbi nozik psixologik kuzatishlar orqali ochiladi. Shoir ko'pincha oddiy voqealar yoki manzaralar orqali inson ruhiy kechinmalarini chuqur ifodalaydi. Bu jihat uning she'riyatiga falsafiy ruh bag'ishlaydi. Faynberg she'riyatining yana bir muhim xususiyati — shahar madaniyatini badiiy obrazlar orqali

ifodalashidir. Shoir metafora, ramz, kontrast kabi badiiy vositalardan foydalanib, shahar hayotining turli qirralarini ko'rsatadi. Masalan, tungi shahar manzaralari ko'pincha insonning ichki o'y-kechinmalari bilan uyg'un holda tasvirlanadi. Bu usul o'quvchiga shahar hayotining tashqi manzarasi bilan inson qalbi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni his qilish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Aleksandr Faynberg she'riyati zamonaviy urbanistik muhitni badiiy jihatdan chuqur talqin qilishi bilan ajralib turadi. Shoir shahar manzaralari orqali inson ruhiyati, hayot falsafasi va zamonaviy jamiyat muammolarini ifodalaydi. Faynberg lirikasida shahar oddiy makon emas, balki inson ruhiy kechinmalarini aks ettiruvchi poetik obraz sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Shu jihatdan uning she'riyati zamonaviy adabiyotda urbanistik motivlarning rivojlanishiga munosib hissa qo'shgan ijod namunasidir.

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